

AFTERTHOUGHTS ON THE STATUS OF INTERPRETATION: HISTORIC PERSPECTIVE

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ABSTRACT

The primary task we intend to undertake in the spectrum of this paper is to define the status of interpretation on the one hand, in the dichotomy of written and oral modes of translation and, on the other hand, within the field of translation studies. Are established the main contours of interpretation in the frame of other disciplines too.

Through the lens of various theoretical frameworks, the article examines interpreting as a dynamic process, encompassing linguistic decoding, cognitive processing, and contextual adaptation.

Interpretation is moulded an autonomous discipline and inter-discipline in relationship to pragmatics, psychology, discourse, etc.

Keywords: subdiscipline, discipline, inter-discipline, process, translation, interpretation, translation studies, etc.

It is well – acknowledged that functionally, interpreting and interpretation are the descriptive words for the *activity*. An interpreter is a person who conveys a thought or expression of a source language in “real-time”.

Interpreting is regarded as a translational activity, as a special form “Translation”. It is an ancient human practice that clearly predates the invention of writing - and (written) translation. The English word “interpreter”, in contrast, is derived from Latin *interpret* (in the sense of “expounder”, “person” explaining what is obscure”), the semantic roots of which are not clear, the Latin term *interpret*, denoting someone “explaining the meaning, “making sense of” what others have difficulty understanding, is a highly appropriate semantic foundation for “interpreter” and “interpreting” in our current understanding. (F. Pöchhacker, 2005 p. 9-10).

Interpreting as the activity of enabling or facilitating communication between speakers of different languages is a millennial practice, with records dating back some five -thousand years.

Before embarking upon a status of interpretation in the spectrum of translation studies, it is helpful to make some touches upon the relationship between interpretation and translation from a historic perspective.

Though it is difficult to trace the history of early interpreting activities (Phelan, 2001), the assumption that interpreting belongs to one of the oldest professions in the world is due to the use of oral activities in transferring messages from one tribe to others; various tribes with different languages communicate each other. D. Andres emphasizes the roles of interpreters in social and political aspects of humans’ lives. He mentions about the evidence of the first interpreters in Egypt where interpreters facilitate foreigners to ask for foodstuff from Tuthankhamun. Or the interpreters in Spain helped the communication of three different cultures: Christians, Jews and Muslims. The first interpreters, usually became interpreters by ancient as they were able to speak more than one language and offered to do interpreting activities (Phelan, 2001). Interpreting activities became very paramount during the colonial era when people from different nations started to communicate with one another and the roles of interpreters were recorded vividly. After the expansion, Columbus brought several Indians when he came back to Spain.

Columbus asked these Indians to learn Spanish so that they could help him communicate with the indigenous when he traveled back to central America.

As for conference interpreting it appeared in 1919 after English started to be the first international language replacing French. At that time, the US President, Woodrow Wilson, and The Prime Minister of the UK Lloyd George, were to speak French. That was the first existence of conference interpreting which was conducted with consecutive interpreting. Started from that era, interpretation has evolved into a prestigious profession and the phenomenon of interpreters by accident has changed into professional interpreters following the establishment of interpreting trainings, and interpreting organizations.

Interpreting studies as an academic discipline has its origins in the late 20th century. In the history of scholarship on translation, few authors reflected specifically on what we now call “interpreting“. From Cicero the focus was on written translation. One of the few pre-twentieth-century authors who bothered to write about oral “interpreting “at some length was the German theologian Frederich Schliermacher. The scholar described it as “a merely mechanical task” – rendering of verbal material in the words of another language. This speculation on the process of translation became the main concept of interpreting characterizing the latter as an automatic operation. Such an approach is neatly captured in the basic model by Daniel Gile (1994:40); a “process P acting on an input I and producing an output O”

Figure 1. I– [P] – O

The generic process depicted in Figure 1. views interpreting as an essentially linguistic process is supported by Roger Glémet (1958).

He was a senior conference interpreter who held that interpreters transfer speeches “with the same faithfulness as sound amplification” (1958:106). Apart from this linguistic approach to interpreting a group of scholars shared a keen *psychological* interest in interpreting. Aside from

D. Gile’s dictum that interpretation should be faithful to the original, most authors have echoed

Herbert’s basic tenet that an interpretation should “re-express the original speaker’s ideas and the manner

of expressing them as accurately as possible and significant omissions” (p.14).

Gerver’s work published in the 1970 did much to establish the view of interpreting as “ a form of complex human information processing involving the perception, storage, retrieval, transformation and transmission of verbal information (1975:, 119), that is widely held in the interpreting community to this day. The psychological approach is based on the view of language as a code and the linguistic conversion process is referred to as “transcoding, that is, decoding and subsequent (re-)encoding by the human”.

Interestingly, Gerver’s work to the 1970s was not the only “psychological approach” to interpreting:

Danica Seleskovitch, a pioneer professional and interpreter trainer, sought to explain the process of interpreting even in her earliest publications (e.g. Seleskovich 1962). Her main interest lay in the mental process leading from the speaker’s utterance to the interpreter’s rendition. She was mainly interested in processing operations such as short -term memory and knowledge use. Kohn and Kalina(1996) supported psychological approach too. Their research is based on the conceptualization of interpreting as “text processing”.

The triangle structure defines interpreting as process driven by human agents such as a speaker, isteners and the interpreter. It’s a communication in a particular situational context, which in its turn is shaped by a given social-cultural environment. The interpreter is envisaged as a bridge between the situational and socio-cultural backgrounds.

The various conceptualization of interpreting outlined above may differ widely with regard to their origin and theoretical frameworks, nonetheless, they all share a basic view of interpreting as a “process”.

By Interpreting, an interpreter has several advantages:

- More freedom than translator;
- Concentrate on the sense of message rather than the words which convey it;
- Get helpful aids from the intonation, gesture and facial expressions of the speaker (non-verbal language);
- Occasionally ask the speaker to repeat a word, a phrase or a sentence or explain some points.
- Require less precision than that of a translators’.

Interpreter faces:

- a) Stress
 - Great demands on the interpreter ability to seize the essential meaning;

In this case interpreting is labeled as a *communication process*.

We shall begin by tracing some influential ways of thinking about the phenomenon of interpreting most of which can be shown to involve the notion of “process”.

What is a process? Let’s dwell upon the various meanings attributed to the concept of “process”.

Webster’s (1984) Third New International Dictionary offers a wealth of definitions. Aside from more technical uses, a “process” is described most generally as a” continued onward flow”, or “course” as “something” (as a series of actions, happenings, or experiences) going on or carried on”; and as “the action of continuously going along through each of a succession of act events, or developmental stages (1986: 1808). All these definitions are used in a narrower sense, while a “process” is also defined in a wider sense, i.e. as a course of (human) actions and not a set of specified operations.

The constituents of the process, whether linguistic units or mental constructs have often been modeled in a fundamental tripartite structure proposed by D. Seleskovitch:

- Concentrated listening, absorbing information and reproducing it;
- b) Pressure
 - Psychological pressure
 - Rapid analysis and synthesis
 - Immediate communication on
- c) Linguistic competence: source language and target language.
 - Phonological, syntactic and semantic differences between English and Armenian
 - Lack of general cultural and background knowledge.
 - Different accents: Different speakers with varied accents

Thus, we have sufficient ground to assume that interpreting is a *complex process*; is a process involving many constituent processes in the ways of a triadic process of interaction. There are various ways of seeing and modeling interpreting: *linguistic approach, cognitive approach and a functional approach to interpreting*.

A handful of individual research efforts devoted to aspects of interpreting were made in various fields in the first decades of the last century, but it was not until the 1970s that a primary interest in interpreting emerged. The name “interpreting studies as a discipline, analogous to translation studies first appeared in

a scholarly paper in the early 1990s (Salevsky, 1993). While the name of the field has been settled, *its nature remains an issue of debate*.

Further insights into this designation is gained in the light of considering the relationship between *translation and interpretation*. We don't have a uniform approach to the status of interpreting.

A fundamental question regarding the nature of interpreting studies concerns its relationship with the field of translation studies Miriam Shlesinger had characterized interpreting studies as "a subdiscipline" in translation studies (1995), elegantly hinting at its subordinate status as well as emphasizing its potential for further autonomous development. The issue of their subdisciplinary relationship however, remains: while it is widely accepted that interpreting studies has a place within translation studies (F. Pöchhacker 2015). In a similar vein, Klaus and Kaindl, Anthony Pyn touch on the nature of interpretation, seeing it as a sub-discipline within a broader field of translation studies. Interestingly, enough, Lawrence Venuti's work "The Translator's Invisibility" highlights the importance of interpretation within translation, positioning translation as a sub-discipline of interpretation. There are also a lot of opinions stating their autonomous disciplinary character as "translation and interpreting studies." The question of working within or between disciplines has lost much of its importance in either field nowadays and the issue of its interdisciplinary character is widely discussed now, as "translation and law" or "translation and medicine" "in translation studies. This illustrates the multifaced nature of interpreting studies (Routledge Encyclope Edited by Franz Pöchhacker. London and New York, 2015, pp202-203). Barbara Seidhofer is a leading proponent of sub-discipline nature of interpreting, exploring it within English for Specific Purposes (ESP).

In terms of status interpretation should be moulded an autonomous discipline in the frame of translation studies.

Thus, tackling the relationship of translation and interpretation it should be noted that we can't draw watertight distinction between them. Both interpretation and translation function in the translation studies as two sides of the same entity with two different modes. The main contours of these relationships in ESP is of interdisciplinary character. Both the translation and interpretation descend from a common universal, rather than the latter deriving from the former. In asymmetrical doctrine, they belong to different levels.

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